

Smartphones - Curse or Boon for Productivity at Work Place

Anand B. Dadas¹ and Atul Kumar²

¹Director and Head PGRC, Neville Wadia Institute of Management and Research, Pune, India.

²Associate Professor, Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra, India.

CITATION: Dadas, Anand B. and Kumar, Atul (2017), "Smartphones - Curse or Boon for Productivity at Work Place", *MERC Global's International Journal of Social Science & Management*, Vol. 4, Issue 4, pp. 113-115.

ARTICLE HISTORY: Submitted: August 12, 2017, Revision received: September 05, 2017, Accepted: September 15, 2017

ARTICLE TYPE: Review paper

ABSTRACT

The lifestyle of people in today's society has drastically changed because of the rapid advancement of technology as well as the introduction of smartphones. The purpose of the present research is to study the positive and negative aspects of the use of smartphones on the lifestyle of people personally as well as professionally. It includes distraction in the workplace, the effect on their level of productivity, concentration levels, fast communication and employee morale. The study is based on secondary research. The paper also discusses that though smartphone's negative aspects are many, but implementing the proper policies and procedures in an organisation helps in percolating positive effect on employee morale, their efficiency and productivity. The outcome of the study is that the use of the smartphone is convenient and aids in quick and efficient communication. Smartphones are effective in timely communication and resolving the conflicts in the workplace, even if the employee is not at one's desk, enhances in communicating personal feelings while eliminating the middle person. During the work day, smartphone micro-breaks are found to increase productivity in the workplace, thus allowing the employees to refresh their minds by taking a break off from potential work stress.

KEYWORDS: Smartphones, Productivity, Communication, Workplace.

1. INTRODUCTION

Can you picture the world without smartphones? A time when we used payphones on the side of the street or in the store? I can. It's 1990 and you're waiting for an important phone call- you have two choices which are waiting until you finally receive the call or have your answering machine record it to the cassette tape. Or you are out on the town and need to check in with the babysitter to make sure the kids are alright, so you search for the nearest payphone. You work at a large factory and your boss is looking for you, but it is very noisy and you don't hear the overhead speaker paging you, so your boss sends his secretary to walk around the building to find you. Lastly, you are on vacation and get lost. Hopefully, you have a map in your car or went to AAA to get the latest paper maps. These are examples of what life was like before smartphones were introduced.

1.1. Distractions

There are several types of distractions relating to smartphones which negatively influences and interrupts the focus of many employees. We have all been there- our smartphone screen lights up, vibrates or rings that are initiated from an incoming phone call, text message, or social media notification. This directly contributes to the distractions that exist which impact the concentration level of an employee. It is close to impossible for an individual to ignore any notification, pointless or important, when he or she is in the workplace. It takes a lot of self-control to ignore notifications that do not require immediate attention. Employees can easily become preoccupied with personal conversations via texting or social media. It often will take more time for the employee to regain focus to continue his or her work-related tasks. Research proves that it is easier to tune out a two-way conversation or another employee talking on the business phone compared to personal conversations

conducted on smartphones. There was a scientific study done by the researchers at the University of San Diego testing the effects of smartphone vs. actual conversations (Walton, 2013).

1.2. Texting

Text messaging is the number one form of communication amongst smartphone users. This has influenced the way individuals in today's society communicate with one another. While at the workplace, texting can have a positive benefit of gaining quicker contact of other employees and clients, but it can also interfere with the level of productivity if the amount of time spent texting is abused. Some employees can exceed the average amount of time spent texting throughout the workday, which can decrease productivity and concentration levels. There are daily situations that increase productivity and decrease the amount of time it takes for certain tasks to be completed in the workplace. Employees and clients can send notifications and updates more quickly than an email. An email requires an individual to be logged into his or her email account compared to a text message that is sent directly to a phone number and does not require that extra step of "logging-in." A date or time change for a meeting or conference call can be texted directly to the individual to save time and allow everyone involved to know immediately. This can be helpful for individuals who have unpredictable work schedules or have last minute meetings that are scheduled at the convenience of clients and customers. Reminders can be set for important conference calls or meetings, which would send a notification directly to the smartphone usually fifteen minutes prior. When productivity increases, it drastically impacts the ability to multi-task to complete more responsibilities and meet all deadlines appropriately.

2. THE POSITIVE ASPECTS OF SMARTPHONE USAGE IN THE WORKPLACE

Convenience is a crucial aspect that all organisations and firms look to obtain for their employees. Smart phones provide the ability for employees and clients to communicate and contact one another quickly and efficiently. Before smartphones were introduced, contacting other customers and clients on their office phone and dealing with automated systems was considered the "norm." In today's society, that is almost unheard of since it is easier and more convenient to connect with another client on his or her smartphone since these devices are so readily available. If an individual does not respond to a simple text message, e-mail, or phone call within a certain period of time, this individual can be considered "rude" for potentially ignoring the notification on his or her smartphone. Conflicts are resolved faster when smartphones are a possible form of communication. Timely phone systems or secretaries can transfer errors or miscommunications to upper management or other employees who receive a message while he or she is away from their desk. Contacting a personal smartphone and avoiding the "middleman" between employees and clients can increase the personal feeling amongst the company and its employees (Chron Small Business) Contacting an individual on their personal smartphone can increase the probability that an urgent message regarding a meeting that day or even the next hour is received on time. According to the University of Kansas study "Smartphone Micro-breaks During Work Day are Productive," employees should be given a few short breaks throughout the day. This has proven an increase in productivity and more deadlines being met before or on time. These mini-breaks throughout the day allow employees to take their minds off any potential work stress and "refresh" his or her mind. The University of Kansas study says "workers who use their phones for short breaks throughout the day tend to be happier and have a more positive attitude." According to this study, employees spend an average of 22 minutes per eight-hour workday on his or her personal phone. This statistic is approximately three minutes each hour.

3. THE NEGATIVE ASPECTS OF SMARTPHONE USAGE IN THE WORKPLACE

Communication is extremely important in order to prevent any misconstruing or misinterpretations in the workplace amongst employees, management, HR professionals and clients. Face-to-face interactions have diminished a great deal due to the rapid increase in smartphones. There has been a limitation placed on personal relationships with employees, management and clients by relying solely on technology. According to the resource, *The Negative Effects of Cell Phones* (2013) "relationships in the real world are affected when they are substituted for electronic ones". People in today's society have become accustomed to communicating daily through text messaging, e-mailing, and social media since it is convenient and a quick way of connecting with others. This has a downfall to it, considering no one bothers to pay attention to the people around them. This affects performance, alters relationships, and decreases networking and making business connections with others. Smartphones have become a major distraction in the workplace, which is the main issue that affects the quality of an employee's work and his or her concentration level. According to a study from Carnegie Mellon University's Human-Computer Interaction Lab, "researchers found that the

average office worker gets about 11 minutes in between each interruption, but take about 25 minutes to return to completing the original task after each interruption" ("The Negative Effects of Cell phones," 2013). Networking and making connections are extremely important in the business world today. Long-lasting relationships develop from in-person contact. Even though technology makes it easier to stay connected, this has been negated by making it difficult to begin and maintain relationships without personal interaction. The interpretation of messages and the meaning behind the way certain words are typed and perceived has been drastically changed due to the consistent daily use of smartphones and similar technological devices. Facial expressions and personal interaction play a huge role in defining how an individual feels about something. The way an individual would text or email a personal friend verse a client could be completely different. "Have a great day!" or "Have a great day." could be interpreted differently when typing an email to a client. A friendlier vibe is given by the exclamation point opposed to the period. In both instances, the employee could have meant "Have a great day" in a heart-warming, friendly way, but the punctuation can alter how this is interpreted.

4. THE EFFECTS OF POLICY & PROCEDURE ON EMPLOYEE MORALE AND PRODUCTIVITY

There are certain policies and procedures that can be issued based on the usage of smartphones and other similar devices in the workplace. Some options are: a zero-tolerance policy, case-by-case, break-time only, or a reasonable use policy. In an article written by Rebecca Mazin from AllBusiness.com, she believes that the best way to go about "electronics, communications policy" is to structure it around the organisation's corporate culture. Depending on the size of the company and its corresponding culture, certain policies and procedures could be more or less appropriate. Selecting a policy that is not structured around the organisation's culture can cause risk and negative effects on employee morale and productivity.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Using a smartphone at the workplace has its advantages as well as disadvantages. It's both a curse and a boon depending on its use in the workplace. There are certain policies and procedures that can be issued based on the usage of smartphones and other similar devices in the workplace. Smartphones have become a major distraction in the workplace, which is the main issue that affects the quality of an employee's work and his or her concentration level. When productivity increases, it drastically impacts the ability to multi-task to complete more responsibilities and meet all deadlines appropriately. So, the use of smartphones will increase the employee's efficiency and productivity only if it is used according to the purpose and vitality in the workplace with self-supervision and company norms.

6. REFERENCES

1. Doucette, C. (2014), "Positive effects of cell-phone technology in the workplace", retrieved from: <http://smallbusiness.chron.com/>.
2. Mazin, R. (2014), "It's time to tame workplace texting", retrieved from: <http://www.allbusiness.com/allbusiness-stop-workplace-texting/16706751-1.html>
3. Noell, M. (2014), "Study: smartphone "microbreaks" during the workday are productive", retrieved <http://www.kltv.com/story/26044621/study-smartphone-microbreaks-during-work-day-are-productive>.
4. The Negative Effects of Cell-phones in the Workplace (2013, December 3), retrieved from: <http://polygrafi.com/2013/12/03/the-negative-affects-of-cell-phones-in-the-workplace/>.
5. Walton, A. G. (2013), "Science proves that cell phones are annoying and distracting", retrieved from: <http://www.forbes.com/sites/alicegwalton/2013/03/13/science-proves-that-cell-phones-are-annoying-and-distracting/>.

ABOUT THE AUTHOR (S)

Dr. Anand B. Dadas is Director and Professor at Neville Wadia Institute of Management Studies & Research. He has been working as a Member of Academic Council, Council of Savitribai Phule Pune University and Chairman of HRM Board of Studies, Human Resource Management. He is a Research Guide and Principal Investigator - UGC and BCUD, Savitribai Phule Pune University research projects. He is the corresponding author and can be contacted at drdadas.10@gmail.com.

Dr. Atul Kumar is B.Sc., MBA, M.Phil., PGDIB and Ph.D. He is currently working as a deputy director and associate professor at Siddhant Institute of Business Management, Pune, Maharashtra, which is approved by AICTE, New Delhi, Govt. of Maharashtra and affiliated to the Savatribai Phule Pune University, Pune.